

Use of Uranine Fluorescence Tracer for the Hydraulic Characterization of Al-Faraa Groundwater Aquifer System

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ABSTRACT

Uranine fluorescent tracer was used in a field study to investigate the hydraulic characteristics and hydraulic residence time (HRT) within the Neogene sub-aquifer of Al-Faraa groundwater aquifer system. The need for determining hydraulic characteristics and HRT of Al-Faraa aquifer system is high since all previous studies and investigations of the aquifer system were based on theoretical assumed values. A Pulse single-well tracer method has been adopted and used. The method involves the injection of Uranine water solution over a short duration (15 minutes) followed by water injection allowing the tracer to disperse into the formation and create a drift then the water withdrawal (pumping back) starts and water samples are taken with time. Samples were analyzed for Uranine using fluorometer. The flow velocity and effective porosity were estimated at 9.8 m/day and, 0.04, respectively using a numerical model. This paper describes the single well tracer method, gives details and results of field experiment, presents numerical model results, and a discussion of the scope and limitations of the technique.

1. INTRODUCTION

Investigations of the transport and fate of contaminants in fractured-rock aquifers require knowledge of aquifer hydraulic and transport characteristics including hydraulic conductivity, specific storage, effective porosity, and dispersivity to improve prediction of the rate and direction of movement of contaminated ground water. The reliability of transport and fate of contaminants models depends strongly on accurate identification, quantification, and understanding of these characteristics. These aquifer hydraulic and transport characteristics could be determined in the field using tracer tests [1]. The results of tracer tests are far more meaningful and accurate when compared to similar results produced by computer groundwater modeling using potentiometric lines data [2- 4].

In general, tracer testing can be described as injecting a tracer (usually an inert chemical compound or dye) into the groundwater and monitor its recovery in order to simulate groundwater flow and storage properties or track where it is going. The success of a tracer testing experiment depends very much on careful planning. Management and planning step comes before doing the experiment to overcome all obstacles which may face the experimental outcomes. The outcome of a hydrological study including a tracer experiment is only as good as the quality of the planning that went into it [5].

Parameter determination utilizing laboratory techniques may fail to account for field conditions not captured in the laboratory, e.g., background aqueous conditions, field heterogeneities in porosity and hydraulic conductivity. Field scale tracer studies can also be conducted to determine transport parameters. The scope of tracer studies can range from several to many wells and can use natural or induced gradients. The migration of a tracer past a point can be studied, or the migration of the entire tracer with time can be monitored [6-10].

Groundwater aquifer system in Al- Faraa catchment consists of several rock formations from the Triassic (Lower Cretaceous) to recent age. Geological formations of Al-Faraa catchment are composed mainly of Limestone, Dolomite and marl. These geological formations contribute the attributes of karst formation of Al-Faraa catchment [11].

Due to water resources importance in Al-Faraa karstic catchment for different humanitarian activities and no tracer studies made before to determine catchment parameters such as time and

velocity of groundwater movement, the need of water investigation is necessary to understand the behavior of groundwater movement [12].

Groundwater movement in the Eastern Aquifer in the West Bank has been characterized primarily by wells data and potentiometric surface mapping. Wells in Al-Faraa catchment are drilled in four sub-aquifers. These sub-aquifers are Eocene, Cenomanian, Neogene and Pleistocene sub-aquifers [13].

Field studies to describe hydraulic and transport in karst aquifer were not conducted before in Al-Faraa karstic catchment and for this reason; this study have the potential to significantly contribute to the data base of information available on hydraulic and transport properties of these aquifers.

2. STUDY AREA

This field study will be carried out in Al-Faraa karstic catchment which lies within the Eastern Aquifer Basin, one of the three major groundwater aquifers forming the West Bank groundwater resources (see Figure 1).

Al-Faraa catchment divides into three sub-catchments: (1) Badan, (2) Upper Faraa, (3) Malaqi [14]. The upper Faraa and Badan contain most of the water springs in Al-Faraa catchment and catch most of the rain water falling within the catchment. It lies within the Eastern Aquifer Basin, which is one of the three major groundwater aquifers forming the West Bank groundwater resources. Figure (2) shows Al-Faraa sub-catchments and the distribution of existing wells [15].

The area of the catchment is extending about 30 km over three districts: Nablus, Tubas and Jenin. The estimated area of the catchment is 331 km² accounting for about 6% of the total area of the West Bank. About 60% of the area is Forests and semi natural areas.

Catchment topography is hilly with slopes generally less than 20% and elevations ranging between 920 m above sea level in Tubas and Jenin to 350 m below sea level in the Jordan Valley(See Table 1, Figures 2 and 4, [17, 18]). Soil within the catchment is light brown Rendzina with clay texture and variable depth, but rarely deeper than 60 cm, and with a rock cover of about 30 % [17].

Figure 4 includes summary information on the catchment collected from PWA, 2007 [16] on landscape, well distribution, rainfall distribution, geology, evapotranspiration, and soil classification.

The sub-humid part of the catchment is (18%) and about 82% of the catchment is suffering from various level of aridity ranging from hyper (10%), to semi-arid (32%), and to arid (40%) (see Figure 4, and [18]).

The climate is semi-arid Mediterranean climate, characterized by wet and mild winters, dry and hot summers (about 5 months), with mean minimum and maximum temperatures approaching 13.3 °C and 22.3 °C, respectively [17]. Average annual rainfall within the catchment varies between 250 mm in the south-east near the Jordan River to 700-1000 mm in the north-west areas of Tubas and Jenin. Evapotranspiration rate varies within the catchment from 2350 mm/year in the south-east near the Jordan River to 1850 mm/year in the north-west areas of Tubas and Jenin (see Figure 4).

Table 1. General land cover/use of Al-Faraa catchment

Land Cover/Use	Area (km ²)	Percentage (%)
Artificial surfaces	16.94	5.1
Agricultural areas	115.89	35.1
Forests and semi natural areas	197.17	59.7
Water bodies	0.28	<0.1
Total	330.28	100

Data Source: Dudeen, 2007 [18]

Figure (1): General location of Al-Faraa catchment (PWA, 2007, [16]).

Source: [15, 19]

Figure (2): Al-Faraa sub-catchments and wells distribution map

3. SINGLE WELL INJECTION WITHDRAWAL TRACER TEST (SWIW)

3.1 Background on SWIW

SWIW tests were first developed within the oil industry in order to estimate residual oil saturation in the rock, Tomich et al., 1973 [20], and this particular application was also patented in the U.S. 1971 /Deans, 1971/ [21].

A SWIW, drift and pump back test consists of the following phases:

1. Tracer Injection: The SWIW test involves the injection of tracer solution as a pulse in a well which is penetrating the aquifer and screened. The tracer is injected when the well is not pumping and in one shot (pulse, see Figure 4-a). A specific volume of well water depending on well size and flowing conditions (100-500 liters) is drained in the well immediately after the tracer pulse injection to push the injected tracer into the formation and mix with the

Map's Sources: PWA, 2007, [16]

Figure 3 Physical, geological, and climatological characteristics of Al-Faraa catchment

groundwater flow. It is assumed in SWIS that the aquifer is flowing at steady state and unaffected by regional flow conditions (from other wells).

2. Aquifer Waiting/Resting Time: A waiting/resting time is allowed for the injected tracer to drift into the aquifer. This time is related to a travel distance of 2-3 m far from the well screen (see Figure 4-b).
3. Tracer Recovery: After the resting time, the flow is reversed (pumping and water withdrawal starts) and the tracer-labeled water is removed from the aquifer – the same well. During this withdrawal phase samples will be taken as a function of withdrawal time, from time (0) with tracer concentration = 0 to time (t) with tracer concentration = $c(t)$ and be taken to the laboratory to determine their tracer content. The tracer concentration $c(t)$ will be plotted with time (t) to produce a concentration versus time breakthrough curve (see Figure 4-c).
4. Tracer Data Evaluation: The aquifer-tracer test data were evaluated using analytical and numerical methods. The analytical method was used to obtain an initial estimate of the aquifer properties, with the assumption that the heterogeneous site could be modeled as an equivalent homogeneous and anisotropic system.

The estimation of the filter velocity is carried out by measuring the dilution of tracer concentration $c(t)$ in the well, as a function of time (t). The tracer concentration is monitored continuously after the initial constant homogenous distribution of the injected tracer with the concentration c_0 ($t = 0$) is reached

3.2 Experimental design

a. Aquifer-Tracer Test Design and Execution:

A field study using single well injection withdrawal tracer test (SWIW), drift and pump-back technique was carried out in Al-Faraa catchment in Al-Nassariya village, West Bank, Palestine to investigate groundwater velocity in Neogene sub-aquifer. The reason for using SWIW tracer tests in this study was that extensive multi-well tracer tests may not be possible because there are no verified data on hydraulic connection between two points in order to be able to perform a successful experiment with high tracer recovery, and that such SWIW tests are more or less the only available single-hole tracer test method.

b. Tracer Selection:

In selecting a suitable and efficient tracer for groundwater tracing the following six important characteristics should prevail [22]:

Toxicity: Nontoxic to the handlers, to the ecosystem, and to potential consumers of the labeled water

Solubility: Soluble in water with the resulting solution having approximately the same density as water

Physically: Neutral in buoyancy and, in the case of particulate tracers, sufficiently small to avoid excessive losses by natural filtration

Measurements: Unambiguously detectable in very small concentrations

PH resistant: Resistant to adsorptive loss, cation exchange, photochemical decay, and quenching by natural effects such as pH change and temperature variation

Cost: Reasonably inexpensive and obtainable

Uranine (sodium fluorescein - $C_{20}H_{10}Na_2O_5$), a fluorescent tracer dye which is classified as an artificial tracer, was found to fulfill all above conditions in addition to having an extremely low

Figure 4 Schematic of single well injection withdrawal tracer test (SWIW), (a) tracer injection phase, (b) waiting phase, and (c) tracer pumping back phase

The location Of tested well

Legend

● wells locations

Source: PWA, 2007 [16]

Figure 5 Satellite image of the study area with testing well location

detection limit of $\sim 0.005 \mu\text{g/L}$ [5, 23, 24]. Uranine is an orange powder that turns a bright green to yellow color when small quantities are diluted with water.

c. Injection Well Selection:

The chosen injection well is well no. 18-18/031, is a shallow borehole. Figure (5) is an aerial map of the study area with testing/injection and the distribution of nearby wells. Tables (1) and (3) includes well lithology and general data of well no. 18-18/031 collected from Ghanem, 1999 [24] and Saleh, 2009 [26].

d. Tracer preparation and Injection:

The tracer test was conducted on March 12, 2012. A tracer solution was prepared by dissolving 120 g of Uranine in 600 ml Alcohol with 18 litre of water taken from the well in a bucket. The solution was mixed very well to insure good dissolution of tracer powder. The tracer solution was injected into the test well (18-18/031) as a pulse starting at 9:30 am, and took 15

min to finish. The tracer solution was immediately followed by injection of 100 liter of water to get some of mixing into well casing and to assist in pushing tracer out to aquifer (see Figure 4-a).

The injection of water after tracer injection has the effect of pushing the tracer out as a “ring” in the formation surrounding the tested section. This is generally a benefit because when the tracer is pumped back both ascending and descending parts are obtained in the recovery breakthrough curve.

Table (2): General data of well no. 18-18/03

Aquifer Data	
Aquifer name	Neogene sub-aquifer
Aquifer type	phertatic
Hydraulic conductivity	28.4 m/d
Saturation thickness of Neogene	100 m
Transmissivity)m ² /d(12 - 1137.5
n _e	0.02
S _y	66%
Well information	
Owner	Nader Abdel Hadi
Well no.	18-18/031
X - coordinate	186410
Y - coordinate	183120
Z - elevation	-29.155
Constant pump withdrawal rate	65 m ³ /hr
Aquifer	Neogene (western) (pliocene)
No. of sub-aquifer	653
Drilling year	1970
Depth to water	8 m

Data Source: Ghanem. 1999 [25].

e. Tracer drifting in the formation:

The tracer was allowed to drift under natural gradient for 375 min. This time was taken with respect to calculations done using theoretical data about Neogene aquifer taken from Ghanem 1999 [25] (see Tables 2 and 3, and Figure 4-b). The theoretical calculation for the seepage velocity of water was in the range of 8 to 16 m/d.

The desired waiting time was determined with respect to optimal drift distance which is 2 to 3 meters [3]. During the waiting phase there was no injection or withdrawal of water from the well. The purpose of this phase is to increase the time needed for time-dependent transport-processes so that these processes may be more easily evaluated from the resulting breakthrough curve.

f. Tracer Recovery:

Recovery phase was conducted after the waiting/resting time using the well constant withdrawal pump at a rate of 65 m³/hr to note color disappearing by the eye. The recovery phase was one hour and a half. Samples were taken for every minute of pumping so, 90 samples were

collected in 50 ml amber glass bottles labeled from 1 to 90. The water that pumped was used to irrigate the trees in the farm (see Figure 4-c).

g. Sampling and Analysis:

Samples collected in special bag (in total darkness) and kept at temperature of 4 °C to keep it from photosynthesis and degradation by bacteria. Samples were taken to the lab and stored at 4 °C The samples were analyzed for Uranine content at the Chemistry Department laboratories, Faculty of Science at An-Najah University using Luminescence Spectrophotometer LS50B. The Spectrophotometer has a lowest detection limit of 2 mg/m³. Analysis were conducted according to standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater [27].

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The SWIW tracer concentration-time - breakthrough data obtained from the recovery phase is listed in Table 6 and plotted in breakthrough curve Figure 6 and 7-a. In Figure 6, the temporal distribution of the SWIW test indicating the start of injection, the waiting time, and the start of the pumpback phase, the tracer sampling, and the end of the recovery phase, were shown. The breakthrough data and curve were eventually used in the following sections in aquifer characterization and evaluation.

4.1 Estimation of detention time and velocity

The natural groundwater flow in porous aquifers consists mainly of a laminar movement relative to the hydraulic gradient (known as Darcy’s Law).

$$V = KI/n \tag{1}$$

The following equations for the drift and pumpback test were presented and described by Leap and Kaplan 1988 [4] and Hall et. al., 1991 [28]:

$$V = (Qt/\square nb)^{1/2}/d \tag{2}$$

$$V = Qt/\square bd^2KI \tag{3}$$

$$n = \square bK^2I^2d^2/Qt \tag{4}$$

Where:

- Q Pumping rate
- b aquifer thickness
- K Hydraulic conductivity
- I Hydraulic Gradient
- t time elapsed from the start of pumping until the centre of mass of tracer is recovered
- d time elapsed from the injection of tracer until the centre of mass of tracer is recovered
- n effective porosity

V average linear groundwater flow velocity

Table (3): Lithology of well ID 18-18/031 at An-Nassariyya

ID for the strata	Depth of the strata (m)	Description of the Lithology
1	6	Top Soil, Light Brown with Limestone Gravel, Sub rounded – Rounded
2	18	Gravel, Limestone and Flint, (Medium - Small Size Clean)
3	21	Clay Brown With Gravel (Small Size)
4	24	Gravel, Limestone (Medium Size)
5	28.5	Clay, Brown
6	30	Clay, Reddish Brown With Gravel (Small Size)
7	33	Clay, Reddish Brown
8	42	Gravel With Light Brown Clay (medium Size)
9	45	Gravel With Light Brown Clay (Small Size)
10	54	Clay, Reddish Brown With Gravel (Small Size)
11	60	Gravel, Limestone and Flint (Medium - Small Size) with Brown Clay
12	70	Gravel, (Small Size) with Reddish Brown Clay
Total depth	431.5	

Data Source: Saleh, 2009, [26]

From the breakthrough curve:

$t = 54$ minutes

$d = 375 + 54 = 429$ minutes

To estimate the velocity of groundwater flow and effective porosity using the above listed equations of drift and pump-back test we need well pumping test result parameters. These parameters were obtained from Ghanem 1999, [24] and PWA 2012 [28] as follows:

Hydraulic Gradient, I = 0.015
 Aquifer Thickness, b (m) = 50 m
 Aquifer Hydraulic Conductivity K, (m/d) = 28.4 m/d

The estimation procedures was done as follow;

- Hydraulic detention time was estimated from the breakthrough curve at the maximum tracer concentration, and it was 54 minutes at concentration of 3.889 ppm.
- Equations 2-4 and the pumping well data, above, allow the estimation of flow velocity and effective porosity from experimental—tracer test data as follows:

$$\text{Velocity, m/d} = 9.855008754 \text{-----equation (3)}$$

$$\text{Effective porosity,} = 0.04322675 \text{-----equation (4)}$$

Table 4 Tracer breakthrough data obtained from the recovery phase

No. of sample	Sample Time (min)	Tracer Concentration (ppm)	No. of sample	Sample Time (min)	Tracer Concentration (ppm)
1	6	1.3023	17	54	3.885
2	9	0.2047	18	57	20.398
3	12	0.9285	19	60	19.811
4	15	0.9128	20	63	7.874
5	18	0.3701	21	66	20.553
6	21	0.1744	22	69	17.379
7	24	0.8293	23	72	19.811
8	27	2.1787	24	75	10.156
9	30	0.9478	25	78	11.189
10	33	0.7113	26	81	13.011
11	36	2.6667	27	84	9.723
12	39	1.7005	28	87	7.203
13	42	1.7481	29	90	3.142
14	45	1.3471	30	93	0.996
15	48	1.8922	31	96	0.343
16	51	2.2702			

4.2 Estimation of Recovery and Tracer Mass

Estimation of Uranine dye mass and recovery was done by calculating the total recovered tracer mass (pumping rate multiplied by concentration and unit elapsed time) and plot it versus elapsed time (Figure 7-b).

From Figure 7-b, the total estimated tracer mass recovered was 129.4 grams which means that it exceeds the injected amount by 7.8%, a result is very acceptable for such type of heterogeneous conditions. The total estimated tracer mass recovered at the maximum tracer concentration was about 73 grams which represent about 56.4% of the total recovered.

Figure 6 Schematic Tracer Intensity Progressions during SWIW Tracer Test

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions are drawn in relation to the use of Urinine fluorescence tracer for the hydraulic characterization of Al-Faraa groundwater aquifer system:

- The single-well injection withdrawal (SWIW) test, a tracer test utilizing only one well, was proved to be useful contribution to groundwater characterization, as well as providing parameters relevant to transport and dispersion of contaminants.
- Urinine (sodium fluorescein - $C_{20}H_{10}Na_2O_5$) was proved to be a suitable tracer to be used in karstic aquifer's tracer testing and verified from field SWIW experiment.
- Results obtained were in good agreement with published data for similar conditions and could be used for Al Faraa aquifer qualitative and quantitative modeling.

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Figure 7 Breakthrough Tracer Concentration-Time Curve

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